

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE ACTIVITIES OF THE ENLIGHTENER MUHAMMAD TAGHI SIDGI AND THE ROLE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

At the XIX century, the Russian occupation of the people against siastin the Renaissance began with the resistance of the second half of the century European Enlightenment and criticism of the idea of independence in Turkish national thinking as a result of its synthesis with the views of realism, it is unique in Azerbaijan, in the East and in the West Azerbaijan, which has no analogues, "contains individualism" Islam-Turkish-European content formed a democratic movement. Mahammad Taghi Sidgi (*full name: Safarov Mahammad Taghi Karbalayi Safar oglu*) was an Azerbaijani educator, poet, publicist, philosopher, great thinker and founded The Akhtar School in Ordubad city of Nakhchivan AR.

As a teacher, literary critic, philosopher and geographer, educator, enlightener, enlightenment ideas, artistic creativity and scientific-pedagogical works are widely covered in this article as an important event of the enlightenment movement of the late XIX and early XX centuries and enlightenment-realist literature. His ideas and many-sided activities have resonated and gained recognition not only in Azerbaijan, but also in the Caucasus, Turkey and Iran.

In 1892, with the help of visitors such as Hajaga Faqir, Sultan Khangarli, Hussein Ismailov, and Salman Saskatchewan, a new national school called The Star (Akhtar) opened in Ordubad. Sidqi was both the founder and leader of the school, both a teacher and a writer. There were both law and secular sciences, students sitting at parties, and learning in new ways.

Tagi Sidgi was a broad-minded enlightened intellectual with universal scientific knowledge. For the first time in this article, his life and activities were studied on the basis of materials from the newly opened House Museum of the philosopher-educator. This article is important for bringing innovation to science and providing benefits.

The article focuses on the activities of the enlightener Mohammad Taghi Sidgi at the beginning of the IX century and the role of the Akhtar School in the development of Education.

Keywords: Mohammad Taghi Sidgi, Educator, Ottoman Period, Mekteb-i Akhtar

According to Asadullasoy (2022) the prose creations of the representatives of Nakhchivan literary environment of the beginning of XX century are interesting from the point of view of real and visual refinement of the linguistic picture of the period. Our writers built the way of thinking, social positions of various series of images in their own way, gave a wide place to colorful artistic images and means of expression in the speech of the bearers of the individual style. In artistic prose, the linguistic features of the era, the manner of speaking were reflected in the speech of both the author and the poets. The writers applied to the shades of dialect locally, reflected in the language of images as they came to the place of 'loru, vulgar (swear)' words and expressions that create emotionality and expressiveness, fully presented in their works the metaphorical possibilities of the language, the semantic capacity of national expressions. In the artistic examples involved in the study, the typical speech and lively speech of the characters, by the way, the dialect lexicon, obsolete words and borrowings, term-specific words are widely included.

The most important of them is Sidgi Muhammad Tagh. Sidgi Muhammad Taghi (pseudonym of Mahammad Tagi Karbalai Safarov) (1854-1903) - educator, publicist, poet. the creed and contemporary

of. He received his first education in Ordubad under Mullah Mohammad Tagi Akhund, and then studied at Huseyn Soltan Madrasah. For some time he also lived in Iran - in the cities of Khorasan, Sabzivar, Nishapur, continued his education and was engaged in trade. He returned to his homeland in 1885 year, worked as a laborer. The Teahouse, which he opened with the intention of keeping his family alive, soon became the main gathering place for the local intelligentsia. Here are newspapers brought from Turkey, Iran and Russia, works of Oriental classics, as well as the poems of the members of the literary Assembly "Anjümanu-Shu'ara", of which he was an active member, were read and discussed (Jalil Mammadquluzadeh Ensiklopedy, 2012).

His main works consist of large-scale verse "Masnaviyati-spirituality", verse story "El-Nasir", literary-philosophical treatise "statue-a look at man" (published in 1912 as a book), more than 20 stories. Sidgi created the first adult examples of Azerbaijani children's prose. In these works, known as "school stories" ("school attendance", "the story of a blind child", "lying child", "generous child", etc.) he artistically promoted his Enlightenment ideas, pedagogical views, high spiritual and moral qualities. On his initiative in the school "upbringing" The 100th anniversary of Pushkin's birth was held (1899), and Sidgi made a report on

this occasion (published in 1914 as a booklet). Sidgi also worked in the field of journalism: "Tercuman" (Bakhchisaray), "Akhtar" (Istanbul), "Hablulmetin" (Calcat), "Kaspi" (Baku), "Nasiri" (Tabriz), etc. he worked closely with newspapers and occasionally published articles. He took the initiative to launch a newspaper called "Chirag" in his native language (Nakhchivanın görkemli şahsiyyetleri ansiklopedisi, 2019).

In the Nakhchivan Enlightenment movement at the end of the XIX century he took an active part as one of the leading figures. He was one of the main organizers of a number of literary and cultural And the family of those who are nearer to him. He was a great friend of Mirza Jalil.

In 1892, Ordubad with the help of the enlightened intellectual Huseyn Soltan Kangarli, he founded a new type school called "Akhtar" ("Ulduz"). S.founded in Nakhchivan in 1894, "School-Education" became one of the main centers of the educational movement and literary and cultural environment in the city. M. this gave high marks to the school. S. he began his creativity by writing ghazals in the classical style. Under the influence of the Enlightenment Movement, which began among the Muslim population of the Empire in the last quarter of the XIX century, he expanded the range of his creativity, creating an enlightened realist poem ("Masnaviyati-madaniyya"). the children's literature ("Kaaba Nasir", "Admonition to Mahammadali", "son", etc.); to the relics of school textbooks ("concise geography", "contribution benat"), scientific and mass journalism ("statue-a look at a man", "Pushkin", "the crown dress painting of the Emperor-Azam... speech"), created the pedagogical treatise ("Sampleyi-oxlaq") (Sidgi, 1967).

School-education was founded in 1894 by the prominent educator-educator Mohammad Tagi Sidgi in Nakhchivan. At school, serious attention was paid to teaching secular subjects, along with the native language, the Russian language and literature were taught. In 1896, a new building was built for the school. Haji Zeynalabdin Tagiyev and Lieutenant-general Ismayil Khan Nakhchivanski were closely assisted in its construction. In a short time, the school became one of the Centers of the literary and cultural life of Nakhchivan. Theatrical performances were shown here with the participation of the local intelligentsia, discussions of literary works were held, and anniversary evenings were organized. At the anniversary evening on the occasion of the 100th anniversary of Alexander Pushkin (may 26, 1899), Muhammad Taghi Sidgi made a report on the life and work of the poet. Jalil Mammadguluzadeh called this school "darulurfan for teenage teachers and writers". In 1896, when he became a Russian-tatar (Russian-Azerbaijani) school, the honorary supervisor of the school was Bahram Khan Nakhchivanski, then he was given his place to retired rotmeister Jafargulu Khan Nakhchivanski, and then Mirza Alakbar Sulleymanov was appointed head of the school in 1897, according to his own words (Habibayli, 2004).

Education in Nakhchivan, which is an integral part of Azerbaijan, has always been paid attention and cared for. At the end of the 19th century, the establishment of

a new type of urban and emergency educational institutions began in Nakhchivan. Mahammadtagi Sidgi, who opened "Akhtar" (1892) schools in Ordubad and "Tutu" (1894) schools in Nakhchivan, had a great contribution to the spread of this type of schools. M.Sidgi also founded the first secular girl School in Nakhchivan (1896). Educational institutions such as "local schools", "school-charity" and "Rushdiya" have also been created. M. in the development of enlightenment in Nakhchivan. T.Sidgi, J.And, Indeed, P.M.A.Sulleymanov, A.M. Khalilov, M.Kengerli, M.Qarayev. (Ilkin, 2011).

According to Amiraliyeva (2018) "Muhtasar geography treatise" is considered the first geography textbook in Azerbaijan. Sidgi rendered exceptional services in formation of scientific, cultural and educational environment in Nakhchivan. In this regard, national leader Heydar Aliyev said: "The Thinker Mohammad Taghi Sidgi played a big role in the development of education and culture in Nakhchivan." In the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, attracting girls to school was an extremely difficult task. The school and teachers were stoned. Despite all these difficulties, Mohammad Taghi Sidgi founded the "Girls' School" in 1896, conducted educational activities for girls and achieved their education in Maktab (School). Involvement of girls in education in Nakhchivan is one of the main services of Mohammad Taghi Sidgi. He carried out artistic and pedagogical activities in his literary heritage, which is directly related to his activity, more than 300 ghazals, the verse "Masnaviyati - Moral", the verse story "El Nasir", the literary-philosophical treatise "statue-a look at a person" bring his pedagogical activity and pedagogical views to the center of attention. That is, to what extent is its science and enlightenment, as well as its value and price. Evil was the true value of a person, consisting of what he knows and learns, which is produced by school". Sidgi highly appreciated the role of the teacher along with the school. It is natural that a school loses its importance without a teacher. School without teacher similar to a waterless mill. They are the teachers who enlighten the spiritual and enlighten the mind and soul of the students. Thus, Sidgi said: "the school is like a body. Its soul is a teacher. It is necessary for the teachers of the school to be with knowledge and education". Sidgi would advise students to appreciate their teachers, love them, respect them and protect their population.

Also for some reason, few of the authors who wrote about the formation of the idea of independence in the XIX century touched upon the role of these literary councils in these processes, and in most cases presented them as foci of classical serfdom and conservatism far from public life. In fact, in the XIX century the idea of independence either appeared in these assemblies, or found satisfaction from the literary-scientific, artistic-journalistic, socio-political activities of the people who worked in these assemblies (Rustemhanli, 2019).

According to Habibbayli (2014) In this school, for the first time in the history of our pedagogical thought, it was the practice of "rules of decorum", developed by Sidgi himself and still preserved, which followed its

importance. No criminal measures were taken against the students

The lessons of morality, which firmly took its place in the conference area, also brought Sidgi great fame. This school is especially focused on language education, especially mother tongue education.

In this school, for the first time in the history of our pedagogical thought, the "rules of decorum" developed by Sidgi himself and still preserved without losing their importance were applied. No criminal measures were taken against the students.

Graduates of the School (Mekteb-i Terbiye):

Huseyn Javid (great writer)

Alirza Rasizade (brother of Huseyn Javid)

Mammad Said Ordubadi (great writer)

Aziz Sharif

Rza Tahmasib Bayzade

Məmmədhuseyn Tahmasib

Rzagulu Najafov

Aligulu Qamkusal brothers

Alakbar Abbasov (Alakbar Garib Nakhchivanli),
writer, translator

Ali Sabri Gasimov

Mirjafar Mirishli

Bahrüz Kangarlı (great artist)

Khalil Agha Hajilarzade

Hasan Safarlı

Mammad Khalilov

Ali Khalilov

Heydar Vezirov

Asad Sheikhov

Qasim Bey Jamalbayov

Aga Bektashov

Asadulla Bektashov

Ibrahim Abilov (first ambassador in Turkey)
(Habibbayli, 2004).

However Sidgi, a prominent literary critic, a skilled educator, a school critic, wrote and created valuable works on training and education, our language and literature. ("Example of morality", "contribution - Banat, or a gift to girls", "concise geography treatise", "Tanviri Afkar" ("illumination of thoughts"), "doctor's words", "exhortation", "pedagogy").

This school of Sidgi's soon gained great fame and became widespread in the country. Similar schools began to be established in different parts of Azerbaijan and Georgia. He was invited to Nakhchivan in 1894 by the Nakhchivan intelligentsia also founded a new school – "Terbiye", which is popular in the near and Middle East, here in Nakhchivan.

In the "school of education" both Sharia and secular subjects were taught. Here are "Turkish language", "Turkish hosnkhat", "Persian language", "scientific-divine", "Russian language", "moral issues", "Song", etc. such subjects were taught. From the compiled program of the disciplines, it becomes clear that in most of the lessons, preference was given to teaching moral-didactic stories, poetry and fables. (Huseynzadeh, 2014).

The morality lessons, which have firmly taken their place in the curriculum, have also brought Sidgi great fame. This school is especially focused on language teaching, especially mother tongue teaching.

A talented poet, as a writer. Russian Arabic and Farsi, Sidgi has written enlightening and enlightening poems and stories for children, adolescents and young people, has translated from Russian, Arabic and Persian, has rendered valuable services in the development of our theater, has brought together intellectuals such as Gurbanali Bey Sharifzade, Mirza Nasrullah Amirov, Cumshud Pasha Sultanov, created "amateur actors union", directed it himself, acted as both director and performance actor.

I'm distracted from learning. The "Gift to Girls" lesson, on the other hand, was left out of scientific and scientific analysis. Mohamed Taghi Sidqi, a great educator and prominent educator, died suddenly on December 9, 1903, in the village of Cambodia in present-day Khangarli, and was buried in Nakhchivan. The loyalty of a distinguished educator poet and educator has become a national mathematical ceremony (Habibbayli, 2022).

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